

Enhancing Applications of the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape)

BioSCape Applications Workshop Report, December 2023

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Knowledge holders who participated in the BioSCAPE Applications Workshop held on 22-26 May 2023 at Houw Hoek Hotel, Grabouw, Western Cape, South Africa.

1. Executive Summary

This report presents the significant accomplishments and outcomes of the BioSCAPE Applications Workshop held from May 22nd to May 26th, 2023. The workshop aimed to increase the relevance of decision-making processes regarding the Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCAPE), which is a joint research endeavor between the United States (US) and South Africa (SA). BioSCAPE focuses on the study of biodiversity in the Greater Cape Floristic Region (GCFR) of SA, including the structure, composition, distribution, function, and threats to biodiversity across terrestrial and aquatic social-ecological systems (SES). BioSCAPE utilizes remote sensing data collected from an airborne campaign and field research to study and monitor biodiversity. The Applications Workshop proved to be beneficial in strengthening existing collaborations within the BioSCAPE Science Team, as well as creating opportunities to engage with local end-users, such as data users and decision/policy-makers. Major accomplishments of the workshop include:

- Increasing understanding of the connections between research, policy, and practice in SA, via multi-stakeholder discussions, which helped identify research needs for applications.
- Cementing collaborations between US and SA scientists and end-users through various networking and relationship-building activities, including the creation of third neutral spaces to encourage transparency, enhancing visibility, and co-development of research agendas and plans.
- Growing awareness in South Africa about the potential for new remote sensing technologies like imaging spectroscopy to provide key information needs for the management of biodiversity, natural resources, and risk reduction.
- Growing awareness about opportunities to build remote sensing technical skills for South Africans through NASA's Applied Remote Sensing Training Program (ARSET) associated with the workshop, and training in field methods, science communication, and open-source data management best practices.
- Raising awareness of ongoing and upcoming education and outreach activities, leveraging events such as the NASA Space Apps Challenge and the SAEON Graduate Student Network Conference to engage the wider community in biodiversity and remote sensing-related topics.
- Creation of a network for Early Career Researchers (ECRs) to share resources and stay connected
- Development of a potential future collaboration focused on the blue carbon economy.
- Establishment of a cross-project collaborative working group focused on mapping invasive alien trees.

The workshop successfully aided an effective transdisciplinary research approach with applications-relevance via the BioSCAPE collaborative research field campaign, facilitating communication of needs and expertise in the project's planning phase, and enhancing collaboration and engagement among knowledge holders from various institutions and countries. By fostering relationships across governmental, non-governmental, academic, and research institutions—with special emphasis on conservation, remote sensing, and decision-making—multiple opportunities for applied science were identified and facilitated. Furthermore, actively engaging with end-users demonstrated an ongoing effort to enhance goodwill between the US and SA. Practical next steps include creating opportunities for data sharing and application across the team and document impact stories. Overall, the workshop catalyzed several positive outcomes and laid the groundwork for further cooperation and decision-making relevance and impact of biodiversity remote sensing data.

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2. Introduction: A knowledge exchange and learning opportunity

2.1. NASA's Earth Sciences Applied Sciences Programme

The [NASA Applied Sciences Programme](#) aims to support the integration of Earth Observations (EO) from satellites and related data products into end-users' decision-making activities related to ecological forecasting for conservation and natural resource management. The Programme has been successful in partnering with organizations and research scientists who are using these observations to develop and demonstrate innovative and practical applications that address real-world problems. Some application themes that are relevant to SA's biodiversity conservation needs and cover internationally-recognized societal benefit areas (Koike et al. 2010 and [GEO](#)) are: ecological forecasting, water resources, wildfires, health (including air quality), disasters, and food security. The Applied Sciences Programme also includes climate-related influences and impacts within each of these themes. NASA defines earth science applications as a bridge from basic research breakthroughs to real-world uses of that knowledge. As EO technology evolves, it is increasingly important to incorporate end-users' perceptions and needs to inform data collection and analysis for evidence-based decision-making.

The Biodiversity Survey of the Cape (BioSCape) is a NASA field campaign, which focuses on addressing basic research questions as well as emphasizing applied science for biodiversity conservation while studying the variety of life in the Greater Cape Floristic Region (GCFR) of South Africa (SA) (Figure 1), one of the world's 36 biodiversity hotspots. The GCFR is a region in southwestern South Africa that is home to a wide variety of different plants and animals. This variety is known as biodiversity, and it is important because it provides people with many benefits, such as food, medicine, and clean air and water. The BioSCape field campaign uses remote sensing data, including airborne lidar and imaging spectroscopy, together with field data collected by scientists on land, in freshwater, and in the sea. The research explores the structure, composition, distribution, function, and threats to biodiversity to uncover how and why they are changing in time and space. The BioSCape field campaign is organized around three major research themes that will improve our ability to map and monitor biodiversity in the region and globally:

1. the distribution and abundance of biodiversity (where is biodiversity?);
2. the role of biodiversity in ecosystem functions (what is it doing?); and
3. the feedbacks between global change, biodiversity change, and ecosystem services (why does it matter?).

There are direct benefits of this project to SA, but also direct and indirect benefits to scientists and decision-makers globally via methodology development, scientific publications, open access data and data products, capacity development, and lessons learned. BioSCape's collaborative efforts are built on deep scientific engagement between SA and the US, and as a result, it includes multiple knowledge holders in the GCFR to ensure rigorous, inclusive, and impactful science. BioSCape includes [19 Principal Investigator \(PI\)-led projects](#) with 150+ researchers and practitioners from 22 SA institutions and 28 US institutions. The scientific project is funded by the US government (National Aeronautics and Space Administration, NASA), and the SA government (National Research Foundation, NRF through research grants and in-kind support from the South African Environmental Observation Network, SAEON). The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) contributed funds towards capacity development and outreach activities.

BioSCape underwent eight years of conceptualization and co-development to advance our understanding of biodiversity globally, while also addressing important environmental concerns in the GCFR. This culminated in a 6-week period (21 October-27 November 2023) of intensive field and airborne data collection. Two NASA aircraft - the Gulfstream III (G3) and Gulfstream V (G5) were equipped with a unique combination of four airborne instruments, namely: [Airborne Visible - Infrared Imaging Spectrometer - Next Generation \(AVIRIS-NG\)](#), [Hyperspectral Thermal Emission Spectrometer \(HyTES\)](#), [Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor \(LVIS\)](#), and [Portable Remote Imaging Spectrometer \(PRISM\)](#). Each instrument provides a different set of data for project teams to use with their field data to address their individual project scientific objectives. These data were further complemented by high spatial resolution RGB imagery (Natural Colour imagery with Red, Green and Blue bands) and lidar (<https://www.geolas-systems.com/>) for select sites independently collected by the SAEON/Shallow Marine and Coastal Research Infrastructure (SMCRI) [Airborne Remote Sensing Platform](#).

Figure 1: Map of the BioSCAPE study area where the 19 PI-led projects teams collected field data and where airborne data was captured by LVIS, HyTES, AVIRIS-NG and PRISM instruments. Source: BioSCAPE, 2023.

Remote sensing data have the potential to bring significant benefits to biodiversity conservation. However, there are still several challenges that need to be addressed. These include the need to acknowledge and address parachute science, manage practitioners' expectations, and balance social and financial trade-offs, especially in a developing country like South Africa. To tackle these challenges, BioSCAPE has undertaken initiatives including capacity building for practitioners, promoting community engagement, and facilitating collaborations between researchers and local stakeholders.

3. Workshop format and proceedings

The BioScape Science Leadership Team hosted an in-person workshop titled, ‘Enhancing Science Applications of BioScape’ Workshop (hereafter, ‘Applications Workshop’), which was a five-day event that took place on 22-26 May 2023, at the Houw Hoek Hotel in the Western Cape, SA. The workshop was an opportunity for BioScape Science Team members to engage with practitioners (i.e. end-users and/or boundary agencies that use data, design policy, and make decisions) to discuss specific social-ecological systems (SES) challenges and biodiversity data needs for improved conservation and natural resource management.

For a detailed summary of activities and associated insights for each day, please see [Appendix 1](#) (Days 1-5). This report provides a high-level overview of how the BioScape Applications Workshop successfully achieved its four primary Workshop Objectives (A-D).

The Workshop Objectives were:

- A. Discuss the biodiversity research needs of South African stakeholders and map clear pathways for how satellite and airborne remote sensing data can meet these needs.
- B. Create networking opportunities and cement collaborations between South African scientists and end-users/boundary agencies and their US counterparts.
- C. Build the technical capacity of South Africans by facilitating remote sensing skill building, especially among Early Career Researchers (ECRs).
- D. Enhance goodwill between the South African and US scientific communities, and between South African government and non-governmental institutions and NASA.

The proceeding sections of the report focus on the broader strategies and outcomes associated with each Workshop Objective noting that the outcomes were achieved over multiple events/activities on several days of the workshop programme.

3.1. Workshop Participants

Over the 5-day workshop there was participation from 94 knowledge holders representing seven academic institutions from SA, 14 academic institutions from the US, 13 boundary agency/end-user institutions from SA, and one boundary agency/end-user institution from both the US and UK (see Figure 2 and [Appendix 5](#)). There was a large representation of knowledge holders from SA institutions (63 people; 67% of participants), including 22% of participants from SA academic institutions and 43% practitioners. The US participants (30 people; 32% of participants) were mostly affiliated with the BioScape Science Team and included End-users (1%), Academics (21%), and NASA personnel (10%).

In this report, practitioners are defined as knowledge holders who work for end-user and/or boundary agency institutions that implement decisions and develop policy. We have made a distinction between practitioners from institutions with no research mandate ‘end-users’ and ‘boundary agencies’ that have a decision-making role, but are also mandated to collect data and perform research in support of decision-making needs, for example, the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), South African National Parks (SANParks), the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI). While some practitioners’ sole responsibility within their organization is to conduct scientific research, they are classified as ‘boundary agency’ end-users because they do not work for an academic institution.

Figure 2: The distribution of 94 knowledge holders that participated in the Applications Workshop across institution types and countries. 32% are from institutions within the United States (US), 1% from the United Kingdom (UK), and 67% from South Africa (SA). NASA = researchers, program managers and applications coordinators from various NASA offices; Private = private companies/consultancies; End-user = decision or policy-making authorities; Boundary Agent = decision or policy-making authorities who also have a research mandate.- see [Appendix Table 3](#) for more details.

Of the total practitioners, 27% were from boundary agency institutions and 16% from end-user institutions respectively (Figure 2). [Appendix Table 2](#) includes a detailed list of institutions with a description of their institutional focus and mandate as a rationale for their participation at the Applications Workshop, whilst selected users of remote sensing data for biodiversity are emphasized here:

- The national *Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE)* is responsible for managing, protecting, and conserving the SA's environment and natural resources. This is based on the right granted to everyone by the South African Constitution to have a healthy environment and to protect it for present and future generations. Under the DFFE, two entities are particularly concerned with biodiversity:
 - *South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)* is involved in studying and protecting biodiversity and increasing access to data and information. SANBI's mandate is to monitor and report on the state of biodiversity by regular national biodiversity assessments, which in turn guide public policy on conservation and ecosystem management. Via the management of National Botanical and Zoological Gardens and designing education programs, SANBI raises public awareness about biodiversity and its importance in ecosystem function.
 - *South African National Parks (SANParks)* aids in preserving South Africa's biodiversity and promoting sustainable tourism through collaboration with communities for socio-economic advancement and learning. Operating approximately 20 national parks, of which several are within the BioSCape study domain, SANParks conserves and manages biodiversity in these protected areas by accounting for species distributions, impacts of climate change, and better management of endangered species whilst promoting community-driven conservation and mindful tourism.

- The national *Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS)* is required to ensure that the country's water resources are protected, managed, used, developed, conserved, and controlled by regulating and supporting the delivery of effective water supply and sanitation. This includes the provision of

equitable and sustainable water services of acceptable quantity and quality and the protection of freshwater ecosystems.

- The provincial *Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning (DEA&DP)* is a part of the Western Cape Government responsible for ensuring the resilient, sustainable, and robust future of the Western Cape. DEA&DP has various subsets, including hands-on conservation efforts, urban planning and upgrading, and water and resource management.
 - *CapeNature*, as a subset of DEA&DP, is classified as the chief custodian of the Western Cape's natural environment. They are responsible for biodiversity spatial planning and providing multi-sectoral guidelines for development and the protection of ecosystems. CapeNature's interventions support 113 nature reserves, including eco-tourism and the supply of eco-friendly tools for sustainable agriculture to local farmers, communities, and private landowners. Several BioScape PI-led projects are on CapeNature reserves.
- *South African Earth Observation Network (SAEON)* is a research facility within the National Research Foundation (NRF), funded by the National Department of Science and Innovation (DSI). SAEON's mandate is to conduct and facilitate long-term global change research to inform environmental decision-making within southern Africa.
- The Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) is a science and technology research organization under the DSI that is mandated to improve the quality of life and socio-economic development in SA. It does this through partnerships in the public and private sectors, research, and the creation and distribution of new technology.

This distribution of participation is evidence of a common goal for researchers and practitioners (end-users and boundary agencies), which is to conduct biodiversity research that informs data-driven decision-making within the multi-functional landscape of the GCFR. The sections that follow highlight key achievements as a result of knowledge exchange and learning at the Applications Workshop and the momentum it has provided to foster enduring partnerships between US and SA collaborators on the BioScape Science Team as well as from end-user and boundary agency organizations.

Speakers and facilitators who participated in the BioScape Applications Workshop held at Houw Hoek Hotel, Grabouw, South Africa on 22-26 May 2023.

4. Achievements: Local Needs Within a Global Vision

The sections below summarise achievements according to Workshop Objectives A-D and show evidence of how we collectively worked towards strengthening partnerships between researchers and practitioners for equitable and resilient landscapes. The incorporation of data-driven applications in a state-of-the-art remote sensing project, such as BioSCAPE, holds immense potential for advancing the applicability of Earth Observation (EO) within the regional context, with the potential to scale up nationally. The implementation of these applications could lead to increased efficiency and accuracy in monitoring and managing biodiversity, while also providing valuable insights into the state of the environment. Through the use of data-driven techniques, such as modeling, machine learning, and predictive analytics, BioSCAPE has the ability to significantly enhance our understanding of ecosystems and their dynamics. Such advancements can be invaluable in promoting sustainable practices and mitigating the impact of human activities on the environment. By leveraging data-driven products and/or tools, BioSCAPE can pave the way for improved conservation efforts and a more comprehensive approach to addressing the global biodiversity crisis.

4.1. Biodiversity research needs for South Africa

Workshop Objective A: Discuss the biodiversity research needs of South African stakeholders and map clear pathways for how satellite and airborne remote sensing data can meet these needs.

Understanding the landscape / seascape context to identify how biodiversity data can support planning and decision-making in SA

Biodiversity is a fundamental aspect that is vital for human well-being, good governance, and evidence-based policymaking. However, with the constantly changing environment and the threats to biodiversity, it becomes crucial to have effective techniques for monitoring and mapping this diversity. Biodiversity data plays a crucial role in supporting planning and decision-making processes. One such technique is the use of remote sensing (particularly imaging spectroscopy) and geographic information systems (GIS), which not only helps in tracking changes in biodiversity but also allows for essential biodiversity variables, aquatic ecosystems, and climate change vulnerability to be mapped. SA's rich biodiversity is incredibly important for human well-being and sustainable development because it supports numerous ecosystem services, such as water purification, pollination, and carbon sequestration, which are essential for human survival & thriving economies. However, SA's ecosystems are under threat from a variety of human activities, including habitat loss, over-exploitation, and climate change. That is why collaborative research projects like BioSCAPE are needed to inform biodiversity assessments, prioritization, and planning. Additionally, the understanding of institutional landscapes is integral to comprehending the complex and interconnectedness and complex-adapted social-ecological systems (SES) context of landscapes and seascapes, as well as identifying the needs and potential applications of remote sensing for biodiversity-related research.

In the Applications Workshop, keynote presentations from prominent institutions such as the South African National Space Agency (SANSA), the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON), and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) provided valuable insights into the national applied programs and their role in bridging the gap between research, policy, and practice in SA. In particular, the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) is mandated to monitor and report (to the DFFE Minister) on various aspects of biodiversity, acting as an advisory body, and coordinating taxonomy. Biodiversity-remote sensing data will contribute significantly to local and national efforts (Figure 3), however, there are challenges in operationalizing remote sensing data effectively, including limited technical and

ecological capacity in regulatory authorities, staff turnover, and inadequate communication between environmental remote sensing community and decision-makers.

Specifically, Dr Stewart Bernard, Chief Scientist at SANSA, showcased their institution's potential to develop comprehensive services and tools for supporting space-related activities, which would advance technological and scientific readiness for remote sensing data ([Appendix 1, Day 2](#)). Dr Ryan Blanchard, Fynbos Node Manager at SAEON, showcased SAEON's vision for world-class environmental research platforms for a sustainable society, as exemplified by their provision of open datasets, knowledge products, and dashboards ([Appendix 1, Day 1](#)). Not only does SAEON provide valuable knowledge products and tools to inform decision- and policy-makers, but their research-to-practice value chain also has the potential to greatly enhance the uptake of remote sensing data for biodiversity research. An example of this is seen through the collection (including platform maintenance and instrument calibration), processing, and analysis of rainfall and streamflow data at their sentinel sites across the country. Since SAEON provides access to important and accurate environmental data, and they have two sentinel sites in Jonkershoek and Algoa Bay that are both within the BioSCape study area (Figure 1), SAEON's environmental data could complement BioSCape's field ecology and remote sensing data of biodiversity.

Figure 3: Conceptual framing for the enhancement of the decision-making relevance of data products generated by BioSCape, a collaborative research project. Value can be created with multiple knowledge holders at various stages of the data to policy and action flow. Threat assessments include Red List Index (RLI), Red List of Ecosystems (RLE) and Systematic Conservation Planning (SCP). Regulations include National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (No. 10 of 2004) (NEMBA), National Biodiversity Assessment (NBA) and National Water Act (No 36 of 1998) (NWA). Source: Andrew Skowno, SANBI.

In order to effectively preserve biodiversity and its benefits to people, it is crucial to understand the landscape and seascape context and how biodiversity data can support planning and decision-making in SA. The BioSCape initiative stands out for its collaborative approach, which integrates space systems, field

ecological data, and airborne data. This multi-faceted approach presents a unique opportunity to address biodiversity loss and contribute significantly to the completion of comprehensive and efficient national biodiversity assessments, as mandated by SANBI. See [Appendix 1, Day 1: 'Setting the Applications scene'](#) and [Appendix 1, Day 2: 'Day 2: Understanding the SA implementation context for enduring partnerships'](#) to read more about the contextual insights that keynote presenters shared with workshop participants about what the applied research needs and enablers and common challenges/barriers are in using remote sensing data for evidence-based decisions which are necessary to effectively preserve biodiversity and its benefits to people.

“The diversity, and degree of understanding biodiversity, is unique to South Africa... How useful can airborne data be for applications? What are practitioner needs? How can research serve societal benefits—there’s no bad questions and no bad answers [in this explorative research project].”

– Woody Turner, Programme Manager for the Carbon Cycle and Ecosystems Focus Area at NASA HQ

These collective efforts and in-depth understanding of the landscape and seascape context are essential in tackling the pressing issue of biodiversity loss and securing a sustainable future for all. Therefore, to deepen the understanding of the GCFR landscapes and seascapes and begin to map clear pathways for applications, there was a dedicated breakout session with 10 small groups focused on academics actively listening to decision-/policy-makers as subject matter experts in agriculture, biodiversity conservation, fire and disaster management, management of invasive alien plants (IAPs) and water resources management. The methodology used in this focal group discussion is a social learning evaluation technique called the Value Creation Framework (Wenger-Trayner et al., 2019; Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner 2020). The methodology categorized information by types of value such as ‘immediate’, ‘potential’, ‘realized’, ‘applied’, and ‘transformative’ to determine the importance, worth, and usefulness of interventions ([Appendix 2: Template for Value Creation Framework breakout session](#)). By honing in on the specific details that can make a difference for practitioners, this session successfully enhanced our understanding of how the loss of biodiversity can significantly impact natural resource management. Moreover, it highlighted the potential for bridging the gap between BioSCape research and practical implementation. Through this session, key research needs were identified and valuable information was gathered on indicators that can effectively measure impact and success (i.e. NASA’s nine applications readiness levels), particularly in the use of biodiversity-remote sensing data for decision-making within the GCFR context. This session provided a valuable opportunity to strategize and collaborate on preserving biodiversity and promoting its essential role in promoting sustainable development. Synthesized insights generated will be used to create a separate information brief for enhancing science applications.

“[The most significant thing I learned about during the workshop is] learning more about the ecosystem, and understanding some of the technical difficulties from practitioners”

- US-based academic on BioSCape Science Team

Knowledge holders participated in the value creation breakout session by actively listening to practitioners as they described types of value such as ‘immediate’, ‘potential’, ‘realised’, ‘applied’, and ‘transformative’ related to their research and/or implementation in biodiversity conservation and natural resource management.

Co-developing research agendas and plans

While BioScape is a single 6-week field/airborne campaign focused on research and not intended to produce immediate applications, the objective to identify local research needs and pathways to meet them (Workshop Objective A) was achieved by gathering information and ideas about how satellite and airborne remote sensing data from BioScape, as well as other NASA EO data, can be used to meet end-user needs.

Educating practitioners on the context, potential, and availability of imaging spectroscopy is crucial for collaboration and contribution to research agendas and plans. This approach streamlines the process and ensures end-users' needs are considered. It also promotes appreciation and enhances the research partnership, making education essential for successful and impactful results. Practitioners were informed about existing data (e.g. global research products, such as the [Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation \(EMIT\)](#) satellite data and [ECOSystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station \(ECOSTRESS\)](#)), and plans were discussed on how to use BioScape data in the short term and establish collaborations for future work (e.g. NASA’s DEVELOP programme) ([Appendix Day 4](#) and [Appendix Day 5](#)).

“I have a better understanding of the technology and how this works and what it can currently do and potentially do in future. This allows us to be mindful of how we set up future projects to allow for better integration of remote sensing products. I also have a better understanding of the different projects in BioScape and know who to contact.”

- SA-based practitioner from provincial government

“I have already begun facilitating NASA DEVELOP workshops with both SANBI and the Western Cape government. I will share these insights with my mission and management teams”

- US-based academic on BioScape Science Team

During the fourth day of the Applications Workshop, participants were given the opportunity to engage in a self-reflective exercise designed to collate end-user needs and desired data products or variables in relation to remote sensing for biodiversity. This valuable information was then compiled into a comprehensive 'wishlist' ([Appendix 3](#)), which served as a valuable resource for future discussions and collaborations. Participants were encouraged to review their previous responses and expand upon them, considering whether there were any elements that may have been unintentionally missing or overlooked. Additionally, they were prompted to analyze potential synergies and opportunities that may arise from the combined efforts and perspectives of all individuals involved. This exercise not only facilitated a thorough understanding of each workshop participant's perceptions of research needs and priorities, but also served to foster potential collaborations and enhance the overall effectiveness of remote sensing for biodiversity research.

While [Appendix 3](#) shows a detailed list of desired data variables and end-products, it is crucial to acknowledge the linkages between end-user interests, needs and desired products for science applications related to biodiversity conservation. For example, the necessity for thorough and comprehensive mapping of invasive alien plants (IAPs) will aid in invasion monitoring and strategic management interventions aimed at protecting water resources and biodiversity while simultaneously mitigating risks of detrimental wildfires and erosion. This mapping must include accurate assessments of the distribution, extent, and density of IAPs in terrestrial and riparian zones within national and provincial nature reserves to effectively determine baseline costs of control options and properly plan and monitor eradication efforts. Additionally, strategic clearance of IAPs must be prioritized to ensure sufficient water provision and security. To facilitate such efforts and support water provision and security, the development of a spatially explicit, web-based, accessible information management system for the strategic water source areas of the Western Cape Water Supply System is imperative. This integrated systemic approach will aid in accurate monitoring and planning of water resources. Furthermore, fire risk reduction planning must be implemented at the provincial level to effectively manage wildfire risks, with a specific focus on protecting biodiversity and ecological areas from the destructive impact of fires. An effective approach to this would be the integration of fire and biological control methods of IAPs with conventional clearing methods, accompanied by thorough monitoring of rehabilitation impacts and adaptation of management approaches. It is of utmost importance to emphasize the significance of conserving biodiversity while simultaneously managing fire risks and control. This creates a relationship between conservation efforts and fire management, ensuring the protection of both natural resources and ecological systems. Thus, it is imperative to identify and establish Critical Biodiversity Areas (CBAs) and Ecological Support Areas (ESAs) as part of land-use planning at various levels such as local, district, municipality, and provincial. The inclusion of such areas in land-use planning will provide a specific focus on the safeguarding and protection of biodiversity, therefore setting a strong foundation for sustainable development. By delineating these areas, we can ensure that conservation efforts remain a top priority while effectively managing fire risks and controlling them. This will ultimately lead to the conservation of valuable ecosystems and the long-term sustainability of our natural resources.

During the two panel discussions at the workshop, SANParks, DEA&DP, and CapeNature ([Appendix 1, Day 2](#)); and SANBI, DWS, SAEON and Department of Local Government: Disaster Risk Reduction ([Appendix 1, Day 4](#)) highlighted the importance of remote sensing and GIS in their decision-making processes and the potential applications of BioSCape data. Application needs included IAPs management (species, distributions and densities), water resource management (reporting on dam levels and water quality related to monitoring algal blooms and hypoxia), and coastal mapping for climate adaptation (areas vulnerable to sea-level rise).

There is also a need to embed environmental disaster risk mapping into municipal planning, specifically fire and flood hazard and vulnerability mapping to inform evacuation exercises, and damage assessment - e.g. using remote sensing to map and monitor prioritization parameters for improved informal human such as information on water quality and IAPs and indigenous vegetation fuel loads along wildland-urban interfaces.

These insights from practitioners increased our collective awareness of potential applications pathways for how satellite and airborne remote sensing data can help meet these needs both in the short term (~14 months) and long term by using BioSCAPE as a springboard for future collaborations and early adoption for satellite-based imaging spectroscopy, in addition to identifying funding augmentation needs beyond BioSCAPE (2025+). Moreover, a dedicated 'Open' session was held to plan logistical field work and flight operations for the BioSCAPE field campaign (16 October-27 November 2023). The session included researchers and collaborators on the BioSCAPE Science Team and external knowledge holders in transparent and collaborative planning ([Appendix 1, Day 4](#)). An additional achievement since the workshop was the identification of SANBI's interest in Kelp ecosystems, which prompted the BioSCAPE Science Leadership Team to pursue additional funds to include a kelp project (PI: Bell).

"This was a valuable experience for me. I interacted with a range of South Africans from different backgrounds and expertise. It was also very valuable to see fynbos with botanists/ecologists as this will help build my understanding of these complex ecosystems and help me plan field work and interpret patterns in our data. This was also valuable to connect personally with our South African field team and start narrowing down sample locations, train our field coordinator, and work on logistics. Further, I built good linkages with other projects, both Bioscape and outside. In summary, this workshop was incredible!"

- US-based academic on BioSCAPE Science Team

Photogrid depicts the interactive nature of knowledge holders during various discussions reflecting on applications needs, benefit-sharing and co-planning for the upcoming BioSCAPE field campaign.

4.2. Collaborations between US and SA scientists and end-users

Workshop Objective B: Create networking opportunities and cement collaborations between South African scientists and end-users and their US counterparts.

Creation of neutral third spaces for engagement and collaboration

Several activities were aimed at networking and relationship building – i.e. knowledge holder ‘speed-dating’ on Day 1, BioSCape social with biodiversity-focused wine tasting and local cuisine on Day 2, field trips on Day 3, and an ‘Open’ session for field campaign planning on Day 4. These workshop activities resulted in active participation and enthusiasm, and successful collaborations seen through individuals making connections after the workshop. As intended in neutral third places/spaces for engagement and collaboration, the objective to cement collaborations between SA scientists and end-users and their US counterparts (Workshop Objective B) was achieved by enabling conversations, building rapport, and strengthening relationships. Although we had good researcher and practitioner representation for this multi-stakeholder knowledge exchange event, with limited available resources and capacity, the most relevant local partners were invited and [Appendix 6](#) shows that we also collated a list for future opportunities to engage.

“We should organize a follow-up workshop in 12-18 months to showcase the various products created and brainstorm what still needs to be done.”

- SA-based academic on BioSCape Science Team

“The larger NGOs such as WWF and The Nature Conservancy [are missing in the room]. They are operating and investing in the CFR and would be interested in the potential applications to include this thinking into their future planning and fundraising. Government agencies involved in operations are restricted with funding and limited to invest into testing new and novel methods. NGOs are more flexible to help transition into this space.”

- SA-based knowledge holder from provincial government

Knowledge holders participated in a unique and interactive ‘speed dating networking exercise’ on Day 1 as a way to learn about ‘who we are’ by sharing the most exciting project or activity that they are working on.

The creation of networking opportunities and the solidification of collaborations between South African scientists and end-users and their US counterparts is of utmost importance for furthering scientific progress and promoting enduring partnerships. Through the establishment of neutral third spaces for engagement and collaboration, a platform for open communication and mutual understanding can be fostered. These

efforts have already yielded significant achievements, including the co-development of concept notes within the Western Cape Government's Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning (DEA&DP) and Department of Local Government: Disaster Management. These concept notes, with the support of NASA collaborator Kerry Cawse-Nicholson, were recently considered in the NASA DEVELOP program call. Additionally, awareness of the NASA Space Apps Challenge outreach initiative ([Appendix 1, Day 5](#)) led to the DEA&DP's request for the inclusion of a case study related to storm surge events that have damaged South African coastal areas. This case study was featured in [BioScape's introductory presentation video](#) as a part of the BioScape-related NASA Space Apps Challenge, aptly titled "[Explore a Biodiversity Hotspot with Imaging Spectroscopy](#)". These accomplishments serve as a testament to the successful partnerships established through this initiative and highlight the potential for continued collaboration and progress in the field of scientific exploration and discovery.

US and SA knowledge holders had dedicated time to engage on application needs related to agriculture, biodiversity conservation, fire and disaster management, clearing of Invasive Alien Plants (IAPs) and water resources management as a way to increase contextual understanding whilst building goodwill.

Photogrid depicts the social component of working towards enduring partnerships between researchers and practitioners. Knowledge holders shared meals together and experienced local cuisine and culture, including a 'Biodiversity-conscious wine-tasting' experience providing knowledge holders with information of how the wine industry is contributing to conservation stewardship within the region.

4.3. Scientific Capacity Development

Workshop Objective C: Build the technical capacity of South Africans by facilitating remote sensing skill building, especially among Early Career Researchers.

Overall, the Applications Workshop proved to be a valuable platform for the development of technical skills and the promotion of collaboration among South African researchers and practitioners. It should be noted that 'research to applications sovereignty' within the SA applied science context includes a critical role played by Early Career Researchers (ECRs) as well as boundary agencies. ECRs both in academic institutions and practitioner institutions can be especially important in playing a 'boundary role' as they are often looking for new research opportunities and have relatively more time to engage deeply in a topic.

In this case, boundary agencies are practitioner organisations that can be classified as both data collectors/users and decision-/policy-makers (see Figure 2 above). For example, governmental agencies such as CSIR, Agricultural Research Council (ARC), SANParks, SANBI, and SAEON, include scientific services that collect and disseminate data products in ways that are essential for bridging the research-practice gap, and will ultimately support decision-making. Workshop participants learnt that the NRF has funded two SA-led BioScape projects supporting 25 SA BioScape Science Team members. Notably, several of these team members are affiliated with boundary agencies such as SAEON and the CSIR or are ECRs. The CSIR is a key boundary agency conducting crucial research on water quality and rangeland management. This was evidenced through presentations delivered by the two NRF-funded projects - see presentations by Cho et al. in [Appendix 1, Day 2](#) and van Niekerk et al. in [Appendix 1, Day 4](#). These presentations allowed for a deeper understanding of the importance of the national government's support in furthering remote sensing research in SA.

Skills development around field methodologies for ECRs in preparation for the BioScape field campaign.

“[The most significant thing I learned about during the workshop was] the specific gaps hampering the adoption of remote sensing products in environmental management and conservation.”

- SA-based ECR from academic institution

“I personally would like to learn much more about the technical aspect of remote sensing and classification of hyper spectral images.”

- SA-based knowledge holder from government parastatal / boundary agency

“[Additional information I would like to learn after attending the workshop is] how Remote Sensing is applied in conservation practices in reality. As an early career researcher, I understand how to do the science but I'd like to learn more about implementation of findings from Remote Sensing applications.”

- SA-based ECR from government parastatal / boundary agency

To further achieve the objective of increasing scientific capacity development (Workshop Objective C), BioScape partnered with NASA’s Applied Remote Sensing Training Program (ARSET) team over late 2022 through April 2023 to develop an online course covering the technology and data to be collected during BioScape - [Biodiversity Applications for Airborne Imaging Systems](#). Due to confidentiality considerations we cannot report on whether there was overlap in the individuals that attended both the ARSET training and the Applications Workshop. However, there was overlap with SA organisations that were represented at both events which included, five academic institutions (Stellenbosch University, University of Cape Town, University of the Western Cape, University of Pretoria, University of the Witwatersrand), three end-user organisations (WCG Dept of Agri, DEA&DP and Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve) and five boundary agencies (CapeNature, CSIR, SAEON, SANBI, and SANParks) (see [Appendix 7](#)). BioScape is partnering with ARSET again for a possible in-person training in 2024 as a way to work towards formalising and funding engaged scholarship. Additionally, field trips were co-led by local ecologists and botanists, and regional conservation initiatives (e.g. Southern African Foundation For The Conservation Of Coastal Birds (SANCCOB), CapeNature, SANBI) to increase the social-ecological knowledge of workshop participants ([Appendix 1, Day 3](#)). A couple of

the BioScape PI-led projects (i.e. BioSoundScape; PI: Clark and CapeTraits; PI: Townsend) provided field spectroscopy training for their teams, including ECRs.

Photos of knowledge holders deepening their contextual understanding of the GCFR landscapes and seascapes during Day 3 field trips to Harold Porter Botanical Gardens, Stony Point Nature Reserve, Kleinmond coastal and lagoon ecosystems and the Kogelberg Nature Reserve in the Western Cape, SA.

Additionally, a competitive application opportunity to participate in a future science communication training was mentioned as one of the Outreach/Education events supported by BioScape ([Appendix 1, Day 5](#)). Later

the invitation to apply was extended to the BioSCAPE Science Team as well as ECRs that participated in the Applications Workshop to participate in the science communication training that was facilitated by [COMPASS](#) on 18-21 September 2023. The science communication training included 13 US-based participants of which eight were ECRs and six SA-based participants of which five were SA ECRs. COMPASS is an organisation whose mission is to champion, connect, and support diverse science leaders to improve the well-being of people and nature via science communication and training. In the ‘Bridging the Worlds of Science & Journalism workshop’ COMPASS facilitators equipped participants with strategies and tools to tell different stories about their work, and communicate about the BioSCAPE field campaign and technical aspects about remote sensing in an accessible way.

Furthermore, the BioSCAPE Science Team endeavours to promote data diplomacy and open source data that is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Thus, we are collaborating with NASA via the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC), Amazon Web Services and SAEON to ensure an effective approach to open science ([Appendix 1, Day 5](#)) via quality assured data management - see [ORNL DAAC’s BioSCAPE landing page](#) - and a BioSCAPE Science Managed Cloud Environment (SMCE). See [SHIFT’s SMCE user guide](#) as an example and ideas for BioSCAPE SMCE [here](#) (Lindquist, Currey, Poulter (NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC))).

“[The most significant thing I learnt about during the workshop is] that NASA has an open source policy - and practitioners can utilise a suite of existing data sources as well as anticipate using the findings and data that arises from the BioSCAPE campaign.”

- SA-based ECR from provincial government

4.4. Goodwill between SA and US communities

Workshop Objective D: Enhance goodwill between the South African and US scientific communities, and between South African government and non-governmental institutions and NASA.

Engaging with existing living landscape platforms, networks and groupings

Engaging with existing living landscape platforms, networks, and groupings is crucial in utilizing the potential of BioSCAPE field and remote sensing data. This data can be used in a multitude of ways, including managing invasive species, monitoring water quality, mapping essential biodiversity indicators for climate adaptation, and integrating with municipal planning. However, there are numerous challenges that need to be addressed in order to successfully utilize this data, such as availability, technical capacity, expertise, and budget restrictions. In order to achieve the objective of enhancing goodwill between SA's scientific, governmental, and non-governmental communities and the US scientific community (Workshop Objective D, it was crucial to include workshop participants who are already embedded within existing landscape platforms, networks, and groupings for improved knowledge flow and learning at multiple governance levels - e.g. FynbosForum, Cape Floristic Region Partnership (CFRP), Upper Breede Collaborative Extension Group (UBCEG), Breede-Sonderend Catchment Collaborative Meeting, Berg-Breede Community Of Practice, Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network (EFTEON), Boland-Groot Winterhoek Strategic Water Source Areas (SWSAs) Collective ('The Collective')).

Engaging with existing networks while being aware of the challenges involved in implementation can lead to comprehensive and adaptable transdisciplinary research that is nuanced and iterative. This approach supports the improved functionality for end-users, resulting in benefits such as advanced monitoring capabilities and more evidence-based decision-making. The focus extends beyond biodiversity conservation to include disaster management, water management, and development planning, encompassing agriculture and aquaculture. Perspectives from end-users deeply integrated within landscape platforms are essential for sustaining the impact of BioSCAPE into the future, looking beyond current funding cycles. For further insights, refer to the panel discussion in [Appendix 1, Day 2](#) and [Appendix 1, Day 4](#).

Further goodwill was evidenced by the support received from SA institutions in the form of letters of support and endorsement for BioSCAPE before and since the workshop. Furthermore, the BioSCAPE Science Leadership Team continues to receive invitations to engage and report back at the various platforms: Western Cape Government DEA&DP's Berg River Improvement Project (BRIP) Meeting (9 June 2023) and Ecological Infrastructure Investment Framework Workshop (22 August 2023); National DWS's W. Cape Integrated Regional Water Monitoring Committee Meeting (3 August 2023) and Digitisation of Water and Sanitation Monitoring Systems Workshop (1 November 2023); CapeNature's Central Landscape Ecological Meeting (23 November 2023) and the Cape Floristic Region Partnership (CFRP) AGM and Knowledge Exchange Event (5 December 2023).

Exploring new ways of partnering

The Applications Workshop focused on involving end-users, promoting the use of BioSCAPE products, and ensuring sustainability as another way to achieve the objective of enhancing goodwill between US and SA communities affiliated with BioSCAPE (Workshop Objective D). Enhancing goodwill between SA's scientific, governmental and non-governmental and US scientific communities was encouraged by discussing what is needed for benefit sharing for enduring partnerships. Here, the benefit-sharing session of the workshop emphasized incorporating diverse perspectives and involving decision-makers in the research process for more informed and equitable science. By considering values and goals, conflicts in bioethical frameworks can be addressed effectively. Understanding relevant protocols like the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol can guide decision-making and ensure compliance with international agreements ([Appendix 1, Day 2](#)). Speakers articulated a need for improved coordination and communication between regional governance and academic institutions. Knowledge exchange and improved communication between scientists and practitioners were also emphasized. Due to the audience and limited time, the workshop was limited in addressing the potential of remote sensing data in urban and agricultural contexts and may have lacked focus on specific end-user needs relating to IAPs ([Appendix 1, Day 5](#)).

The overarching ethos of the workshop, as reflected in Workshop Objective D, was to foster goodwill among the scientific, governmental, and non-governmental communities of both countries. As part of this effort, the workshop facilitated the establishment of an Alien Tree Mapping Working Group as a cross-project collaboration effort composed of representatives from various projects, including Adler et al., Townsend et al., van Aardt, van Niekerk et al., Cawse-Nicolson et al., Fitzpatrick et al., and others. This collaboration aims to address the needs of end-users in managing IAP species and further strengthen partnerships in the realm of IAP management. Follow-up meetings (7 and 26 Sep 2023) have allowed for collaboration among the science team and external knowledge holders. These needs are now being documented and will be reported in future.

"[The most significant thing(s) I learned about during the workshop were] (1) The complexity of conservation management in SA, (2) how significant the issue of invasive alien species is in SA, and (3) bioethics - I had not heard this term before but had been thinking a lot about the concepts prior to this workshop, so it was great to put some terminology to these ideas and start exploring further."

- US-based ECR from non-governmental organisation

"Alien plant mapping remains a challenge, yet there is such a strong need! Also that remote sensing has to overcome significant issues before the products can be used, placing the burden on institutions with these skills to share the data freely as the users are not likely to have these skills or the funds to acquire them or the products."

- SA-based knowledge holder from government parastatal / boundary agency

"I really appreciated getting to meet and talk to people from the SA National Parks and to learn about why they are so concerned about invasive species."

- US-based academic on BioSCAPE Science Team

Emergent outcomes

The Applications Workshop proved to be a valuable platform for fostering collaboration and potential future partnerships between US and SA researchers and practitioners. Along with the planned agenda, the workshop also led to several emergent outcomes, such as a side group discussion between five researchers and four SA practitioners (representatives from SANBI, SANParks, CSIR and Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve) with an interest in future collaboration around the blue economy. This highlights the potential impact of the workshop beyond its initial scope. Additionally, the creation of a WhatsApp group for BioSCAPE ECRs (currently 39 members) to stay connected and share resources further enhances the goodwill and relationships between the two countries. During the ECR discussion as a part of the Day 5 Open session, it was noted that future SES research could benefit from including a social science component in BioSCAPE, as it is essential for creating equitable and resilient landscapes that are able to navigate change by anticipating, coping, adapting and transforming in ways that foster equitable outcomes (Leach et al. 2018). This aligns with the global support for ecosystem-based management and governance, including ecological restoration efforts and Ecosystem-based Adaptation (DEA and SANBI, 2016; DEFF, 2019; Gann et al., 2019; O'Higgins et al., 2020). Therefore, it can be seen as a potential leverage point for enhancing the results and outcomes of collaborative and applied research programs such as BioSCAPE. The workshop has set a strong foundation for continued collaboration and potential future research projects that can contribute to the sustainable management of landscapes and ecosystems.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this work has the potential to contribute to practical science applications that support decision-making and contribute to scientific knowledge that broadly addresses environmental challenges such as climate change and land-use local disturbances (such as fire, human activity, and land degradation) to improve the conservation of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Some examples of potential

BioSCAPE science applications include mapping and monitoring the spread of invasive alien plants (such as pine, wattle, and eucalypt) that outcompete local flora, altering fire regimes, reducing water runoff, and worsening the impacts of droughts, thus threatening biodiversity and its contributions to people. The data collected on alien trees can help decision-makers prioritize areas for invasive species and wildfire management. Moreover, nutrient enrichment of marine systems and inland freshwater dams and wetlands trigger harmful algal blooms, killing aquatic biodiversity, and affecting the amenity value as well as the aquaculture and agriculture industries. The data collected on phytoplankton can help in water quality monitoring and the development of early warning systems. Understanding and mitigating such impacts is crucial for preserving biodiversity, protecting human health, and maintaining the sustainability of coastal and agricultural economies. Therefore, the Western Cape Government (DEA&DP, Department of Agriculture and Department of Local Government), SANBI, as well as the national and provincial park systems (SANParks and CapeNature, respectively) are strategic partners supporting BioSCAPE to use research outputs towards driving real change for a resilient, sustainable and inclusive region.

The Applications Workshop successfully cemented collaboration for effective and impactful transdisciplinary research under the BioSCAPE collaborative research project (2021-2024). It created opportunities for knowledge holders (both collaborators on the Science Team as well as external stakeholders not formally affiliated with the project) who may benefit from BioSCAPE to communicate their needs and expertise in advance of data collection (BioSCAPE field campaign: 16 October-27 November 2023). We also considered what a BioSCAPE Community of Practice (COP) might involve and how we could improve ongoing communications, sharing of information, and benefit-sharing in general. In an effort to substantially advance science applications and 'best practices' to avoid parachute science, we continuously aim to maximize the applicability of NASA-funded research by conveying core messages and key findings. Continued positive engagement including active in-kind support and collaboration with end-users is evidence of enhancing goodwill between the US and SA.

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REFERENCES

Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (DEFF), 2019. Ecosystem based adaptation Action Plan and Priority Areas Mapping report. Pretoria, South Africa.

DEA and SANBI, 2016. Strategic Framework and Overarching Implementation Plan for Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) in South Africa: 2016 – 2021. Department of Environmental Affairs, Pretoria, South Africa.

Gann, G.D., McDonald, T., Walder, B., Aronson, J., Nelson, C.R., Jonson, J., Hallett, J.G., Eisenberg, C., Guariguata, M.R., Liu, J. and Hua, F., 2019. International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration. *Restoration Ecology*, 27(S1), pp.S1-S46.

Koike, T., Onoda, M., Cripe, D. and Achache, J., 2010. The Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS): supporting the needs of decision making in societal benefit areas. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Science*, 37(8), pp.164-169.

O'Higgins, T.G., Lago, M. and DeWitt, T.H., 2020. *Ecosystem-based management, ecosystem services and aquatic biodiversity: Theory, tools and applications* (p. 580). Springer Nature.

Wenger-Trayner, E., Wenger, E. and Wenger-Trayner, B., 2020. *Learning to make a difference: Value creation in social learning spaces*. Cambridge university press.

Wenger-Trayner, B., Wenger-Trayner, E., Cameron, J., Eryigit-Madzwamuse, S. and Hart, A., 2019. Boundaries and boundary objects: An evaluation framework for mixed methods research. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 13(3), pp.321-338.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Overview and Annotated Workshop Agenda

Day 1: Monday, 22 May 2023	
07h30-09h00	Breakfast - main restaurant
10h30	Workshop opens
10h30-12h00	Arrival and check in at Houw Hoek Hotel
12h00-13h30	Lunch - the glass barn
13h00-13h45	Registration
13h45-14h05	Setting the scene [Jasper Slingsby, Adam Wilson, Erin Hestir]
14h05-14h30	Setting our intentions for the week [Cherie Forbes]
14h30-16h30	Keynote presentations: Understanding the local context and remote sensing for biodiversity conservation [Jasper Slingsby]
14h30-14h55	<i>NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) [Robert Green]</i>
15h00-15h30	Tea
15h30-15h55	<i>South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) [Andrew Skowno]</i>
16h00-16h25	<i>South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) [Ryan Blanchard]</i>
16h30-17h00	Networking: "Who is who" speed dating exercise [Cherie Forbes]
18h30	Dinner - main restaurant
Day 2: Tuesday, 23 May 2023	
07h30-09h00	Breakfast - main restaurant
09h00-09h15	Recap and check-in [Cherie Forbes]
09h15-09h45	Keynote presentations: Understanding the broader context [Anabelle Cardoso / Adam Wilson]
09h15-09h30	South African National Space Agency (SANSA) [Stewart Bernard]
09h30-9h45	Carbon Cycle & Ecosystems Focus Area (NASA HQ) [Woody Turner]
09h45-10h45	Panel discussion: Understanding local data users and decision-makers needs - South African National Parks (SANParks) [Izak Smit] - CapeNature [Andrew Turner] - Western Cape Department of Environmental Affairs & Development Planning (DEA&DP) [Marlene Laros]
10h45-11h15	Tea
11h15-12h30	BioSCape research talks: Applications Opportunities [Adam Wilson / Jasper Slingsby]
11h15-11h20	<i>Clark et al. - BioSoundSCape: Connecting Acoustics and Remote Sensing to Study Habitat-Animal Diversity Across Environmental Gradients [Matthew Clark]</i>
11h22-11h27	<i>Adler et al. - Impacts of Invasive Alien Species on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning [Elisa Van Cleemput]</i>

11h30-11h35	<i>Merow et al. - TraitsCape: Understanding the role of microrefugia in buffering fynbos from global change [Pep Serra-Diaz]</i>
11h37-11h42	<i>Cavender-Bares et al. - Plant Community Assembly and Trait Evolution in the South African Greater Cape Floristic Region [Jeannine Cavender-Bares]</i>
11h45-11h50	<i>Townsend et al. - CapeTraits: Patterns of Functional Trait Variation and Diversity Across the Greater Cape Floristic Region and Comparison with Other Mediterranean Ecosystems [Phil Townsend]</i>
11h52-11h57	<i>Fitzpatrick et al. - Integrating remote sensing and biodiversity observations to map and monitor plant taxonomic, phylogenetic, and functional beta-diversity in the Greater Cape Floristic Region [Matthew Fitzpatrick]</i>
12h00-12h05	<i>Cho et al. - Hyperspectral signal processing for Terrestrial, Aquatic and Atmospheric Applications (HysTAA) in South Africa [Moses Cho]</i>
12h07-12h12	<i>Wu et al. - Mapping of Phytoplankton Functional Types from Space in Support of Coastal Resource Management and Decision Support Activities [Joaquim Goes]</i>
12h15-12h20	<i>Stovall et al. - BioREaCH: Biodiversity-Remote sensing for Estuarine and Coastal Habitat research [Anthony Campbell]</i>
12h22-12h27	<i>Guild et al. - Cyanobacteria and Surface Aquatic Vegetation of the Cape Freshwater Systems (CyanoSCape): A Hyperspectral Data Campaign and Analysis [Jeremy Kravitz]</i>
12h20-12h30	Q&A
12h30-14h00	Lunch - the glass barn
14h00-15h20	Breakout session: Workshopping science applications using the Value Creation Framework [Cherie Forbes]
15h20-15h50	Tea
15h50-17h20	Equitable research and benefit sharing (Nagoya) [Rachel Meyer, Neil Crouch]
17h20-17h30	Group Photo
17h45	BioSCape Social: Wine-tasting and Dinner
Day 3: Wednesday, 24 May 2023	
07h30-09h00	Breakfast and collect packed lunch - main restaurant
09h00	Field trip itinerary 1: Coastal Ecosystems + Penguins OR Field trip itinerary 2: Penguins + Botanical Gardens OR Field trip itinerary 3: River Valley Hike + Penguins
18h30	Dinner - main restaurant
Day 4: Thursday, 25 May 2023	
07h30-09h00	Breakfast - main restaurant
09h00-09h10	Recap and check-in

09h10-10h30	Panel discussion: Understanding local data users and decision-makers needs - South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) [Nancy Job] - Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS) [Melissa Lintnaar-Strauss] - South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) [Tommy Bornman] - Western Cape Dept of Local Government [Lwandile Nokoyo]
10h30-11h00	Tea
11h00-12h30	BioSCape research talks: Applications Opportunities [Erin Hestir]
11h00-11h05	<i>Rossi et al. - Biodiversity Across Scales: Mapping Taxonomic, Phylogenetic, and Functional Diversity with eDNA, Field Surveys, and Remote Sensing Data [Madeline Slimp]</i>
11h07-11h12	<i>van Aardt et al. - RadSCape: Radiative Transfer Simulation and Validation of the Dynamic Structural and Spectral Properties of the Vegetation of the Cape [Jan van Aardt]</i>
11h15-11h20	<i>Cawse-Nicholson et al. - Intrinsic Dimensionality and Data Fusion to Monitor Cape Biodiversity [Kerry Cawse-Nicholson]</i>
11h30-11h35	<i>van Niekerk et al. - Development of New Hyperspectral Capabilities across Aquatic, Atmospheric and Terrestrial Domains (HyperCAAT) [Adriaan van Niekerk]</i>
11h37-11h47	<i>Brodrick - BioSCape Multi-Sensor Data Integration [Phil Brodrick]</i>
11h50-12h00	Q&A
12h00-12h30	Biodiversity-Remote Sensing Wishlist
12h30-14h00	Lunch - the glass barn
14h00-14h30	Exploring BioSCape's short documentary film (Fishwater Films) [Jeremy Shelton]
14h30-15h30	BioSCape Science Team Logistics (optional) [Adam Wilson, Jasper Slingsby, Erin Hestir]
15h30-16h00	Tea
16h00-17h30	BioSCape Science Team Logistics (optional) (continued)
17h30-18h30	Free Time
18h30	Dinner - main restaurant
Day 5: Friday, 26 May 2023	
07h30-09h00	Breakfast - main restaurant
09h00-09h30	BioSCape Education & Outreach: Overview of current and planned activities [Adam Wilson]
09h30-09h35	Logistics overview and update [Erin Hestir]
09h35-10h30	Open session: Following up with your network [Erin Hestir]
10h30-11h00	Tea
11h00-12h30	Closing session: Reflecting on BioSCape science applications opportunities + Planning your project applications pipelines [Cherie Forbes]
12h30-13h30	Workshop Ends with lunch - the glass barn

Day 1: Setting the Applications scene

Day 1 set the tone for the workshop by reflecting on our diverse Community of Practice's (COP) definition of science applications and our hopes and expectations for the BioSCAPE Applications Workshop and the project in general. The outcomes are described below with a summarised list of insights that come from the Introductory and Keynote presentations to understanding the local context and the importance of remote sensing for biodiversity conservation. Click [here for Day 1 slides](#) by:

- Jasper Slingsby (BioSCAPE Science Leadership Team – Terrestrial PI) – Slides 7-27
- Cherié Forbes (BioSCAPE Science Leadership Team – Applications Coordinator) – Slides 28-38
- Robert Green (NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) - Senior Research Scientist) - Slides 43-79
- Andrew Skowno (South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) - Lead for National Biodiversity Assessment) - Slides 82-96
- Ryan Blanchard (South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) - Fynbos Node Manager) - Slides 99-123

Summarised insights from presentations

- Speakers discussed the challenges of bringing remote sensing data to the decision-making table and the difficulties faced by regulatory authorities and conservation institutions in utilizing this data effectively. Despite South Africa's advancements in tracking and monitoring changes in biodiversity and informing decision-making to conserve ecosystems for improved human wellbeing and sustainable development, there remains limited technical and ecological capacity in regulatory authorities and budget limitations have hindered the use of remote sensing data for conservation management, leading to missed opportunities and weaker conservation institutions. For example, staff turnover, difficulty in enticing academics to engage, and lack of coherent communication with decision-makers also contribute to the issue.
- There is a need for a systematic approach to track and manage the progression and distribution of projects towards integration of the science application into an end-user's decision-making activity. We need to find a more coordinated, collaborative, transdisciplinary and transformative way of working between researchers, practitioners and citizens in the landscape over the long-term with the aim of moving towards greater resilience and equity for all.
- NASA's nine-step index (Application Readiness Levels, ARLs) provides a way to track and manage the progression and distribution of projects towards science applications that bridge the gap between basic research and real-world uses of that knowledge into an end-user's decision-making activity. Furthermore, Communities of Practice and new 'third spaces' (like the Applications Workshop) can help enhance communication and collaboration by providing opportunities for researchers and practitioners/implementers from a diverse group of organizations to exchange knowledge, learn and plan together.

Day 2: Understanding the SA implementation context for enduring partnerships

Day 2 set the practice/implementation scene by collaboratively building an understanding of the SA context and user needs from data users and decision/policy-makers. It began with an introduction from Stewart Bernard, Chief Scientist at SANSA, followed by Woody Turner, the NASA Programme Manager for Ecological Conservation and Biological Diversity. It also included a panel discussion on understanding local data user and decision-maker needs, ten research talks to explore Applications Opportunities from the perspective of the

BioSCape Science Team, a break-out session using the Values Creation Framework for social-cultural learning and assessment of impact, and a discussion on the Nagoya Protocol and benefit sharing which promoting equity and resilience and requires governmental, non-governmental, research and civil society to work collaboratively. Click [here for Day 2 slides](#) by:

Keynote speakers

- *Stewart Bernard (South African National Space Agency (SANSA) - Chief Scientist) - Slides 4-21*
- *Woody Turner (Carbon Cycle & Ecosystems Focus Area (NASA HQ) - Programme Manager) - Slides 22-30]*

Panellists

- *Marlene Laros (Western Cape Department of Environmental Affairs & Development Planning (DEA&DP) - Director) - Slides 34-35*
- *Andrew Turner (CapeNature - Scientific Manager) - Slides 36-39]*
- *Izak Smit (South African National Parks (SANParks) - Senior Scientist) - Slides 40-41*

Summarised insights

- **Keynote presentations:** SANSA has the potential to develop space applications to respond to user needs and the motives for BioSCape, which include advancing the technology and scientific readiness levels for hyperspectral, multi-spectral, Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and thermal missions both domestically and internationally. Moreover, user needs requirements for SANSA's Space Infrastructure Hub (SIH) includes analysis, insight, prediction, and decision support tools. NASA is focused on exploration and discovery rather than implementation. The situation for Earth's biodiversity is dire, with species and individuals being lost. The BioSCape project is integrating space systems (CALIPSO, HSRL, ICESat-2, LVIS, GEDI, NISAR), in-situ ecological data, and airborne data to address this issue. A science applications component is not traditionally incorporated in NASA airborne campaigns and this approach is changing. BioSCape's unique collaborative and integrative research is an example of this improved approach.
- **Panel discussion:** There are challenges faced in responding to understanding of local data users and decision-maker needs in the context of biodiversity and coastal management in South Africa, such as limited capacity and understanding of dynamics of change. Transdisciplinary research could assist in overcoming constraints and barriers faced in acquiring and processing data, the need for translation of remote sensing metrics to ecological metrics, and the importance of engagement with local scientists and users. The potential applications of BioSCape data include invasive species management, water quality monitoring (e.g. monitoring algal blooms and hypoxia), coastal mapping for climate adaptation, proactive environmental disaster risk management and embedding risk mapping into municipal planning, and exploring the role of modeling and prediction in decision-making.
- **BioSCape science talks:** Representatives from the BioSCape Science Team presented on various project topics related to biodiversity monitoring and management in the Greater Cape Floristic Region (GCFR). Presenters names are in brackets '(...)' for each of the PI-led projects which included:
 - ***PI - Clark (Matthew Clark):*** BioSoundSCape is monitoring animal diversity using low-cost recorders and in-situ bird and frog point counts, and connecting these field data with remote sensing to understand habitat-animal diversity across land cover types, fire history and anthropogenic disturbance gradients. This is important for determining the impact of

disturbance on habitat quality to inform conservation planning because if the research finds a strong correlation between acoustic diversity and specific vegetation types, conservation efforts could focus on protecting these critical habitats, thus guiding land-use management decisions.

- *PI - Adler (Elisa van Cleemput)*: By understanding the relationship between the severity of invasive alien tree invasion, the level of biodiversity, and ecosystem functioning, this project can help identify areas with high biodiversity and sensitivity to ecological change, providing a basis for targeted conservation efforts. Also, spatial maps that show the extent of IAPs, water-use efficiency and fuel load are important for disaster risk reduction during extreme drought and fire events.
- *PI - Merow (Pep Serra-Diaz)*: TraitsCape is investigating the resilience of fynbos communities to climate change through understanding the role of microrefugia in buffering fynbos. It aims to contribute insights to conservation strategies by showing the importance of maintaining refuge areas even if there are changes in plant species. By mapping the biophysical environment and associated plant traits and function, forecasting and refugia mapping can assist land managers in identifying regions with higher ecosystem resilience and function.
- *PI - Cavender-Bares (Jeannine Cavender-Bares)*: Monitoring plant lineages (evolutionary traits) rather than species because lineages are easier to detect and monitor using imaging spectroscopy, especially in a complex system like the mega-diverse GCFR. This is important for land management because conserving all the major lineages in prioritised landscape management units will likely conserve evolutionary innovations and functions (e.g. drought tolerance, fire-adapted, IAPs resistance, etc.) which contribute to greater ecosystem resilience and services.
- *PI - Townsend (Phil Townsend)*: CapeTraits project is mapping patterns in plant functional traits using field-based and remote sensing data across the GCFR and comparing the findings with other Mediterranean-type ecosystems. By characterizing the functional ecology, this work is complementary with the enquiry for understanding evolutionary traits (Cavendar-Bares et al.) as the functional traits due to their distinct history, soils, and geology have phylogenetic significance. Increased understanding can better support the long-term conservation and management of this globally significant region, in particular determining where in the landscape IAPs are occupying a “high-nutrient trait space” thus compromising indigenous plant survival.
- *PI - Fitzpatrick (Matt Fitzpatrick)*: By measuring and mapping plant community composition through integrating remote sensing and biodiversity observations (plant taxonomic, phylogenetic, and functional diversity over different environmental, spatial and time scales) in the GCFR land-use managers may gain a better measure of indicators (Essential biodiversity variables (EBVs)) that are key for managing and reporting on biodiversity change. For example, maps of vegetation composition could differentiate between indigenous vegetation that is dependent on groundwater and the invasion of alien trees.
- *PI - Cho (Moses Cho)*: HysTAA is creating a synthetic hyperspectral database using radiative transfer models to assess terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem properties e.g. biodiversity and ecosystem degradation. The application of this is in preparing SA researchers for future spaceborne hyperspectral missions.

- *PI - Wu (Joaquim Goes)*: By developing a hyperspectral radiometric method for mapping phytoplankton functional types (PFTs) in three South African bays (St Helena Bay, Walker Bay and Algoa Bay) this project has significant importance for decision-support for biodiversity conservation and coastal resource management. Managers would benefit from the identification of changes in PFTs, especially the early detection of harmful algal bloom-forming dinoflagellates to mitigate the impact on ecosystems and the fisheries and shellfish industry.
- *PI - Stovall (Anthony Campbell)*: BioREaCH is mapping plant functional types/communities in the field and using biodiversity-remote sensing to understand drivers of biodiversity within estuaries and coastal habitats to investigate potential impacts of climate change on coastal biodiversity. Identifying indicators (EBV) is important for management because estuaries play a vital role in protecting coastlines and maintaining fisheries, and early detection of environmental problems (e.g. sea level rise) improves our climate change adaptation readiness.
- *PI - Guild (Jeremy Kravitz)*: CyanoSCape is mapping plant functional types/communities at a microscopic and macro-level to improve our knowledge about phytoplankton diversity in freshwater systems, and how they change in response to human activities, climate change, and nutrient over-enrichment. By using advanced technology to detect changes in phytoplankton, this project will help managers monitor water quality and potentially aid in developing early warning systems to detect harmful cyanobacteria blooms and invasive aquatic vegetation, which pose risks to human, livestock and wildlife health.
- Value creation focal group discussions: The motivation for this interactive session was to identify how the connection between science and practice can be improved by using the concept of values. Participants were pre-assigned groups by theme, namely: 1. Agriculture and Food Security, 2. Birds & Amphibians, 3. Botany and Plant Ecology, 4. Climate Change, 5. Invasive Alien Plant Species, 6. Land Use, 7. Oceans, 8. Vegetation Monitoring and Disturbance, 9. Water Quality, 10. Wetlands and Watersheds. Each group included a mix of eight to ten knowledge holders from research institutions and practice/implementation institutions. By sharing and learning about value creation stories through specific questions (Wenger-Trayner et al., 2019; Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner 2020), we uncovered potential indicators to measure impact (i.e. hidden values and non-values) by reflecting on practitioners' experiences in bridging the research-practice gap when operationalizing biodiversity conservation and natural resource management. This approach can help determine the success of using biodiversity-remote sensing data as an evaluation tool for funders such as NASA. Synthesized insights generated from this will be presented in a separate information brief for enhancing science applications.
- Equitable research and benefit sharing (Nagoya Protocol): This session highlighted the importance of 'serving nature' and the different approaches that can be taken. It was an appropriate session to follow the value creation focal group discussion as it emphasized the need for input from decision-makers and the consideration of their values and goals. The speakers highlighted the challenges and conflicts that can arise in bioethical frameworks, the need for honesty about uncertainty, and explored the question of who speaks for nature and the importance of informed decision-making. The session also provided background information on the policy landscape, including the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol. It also discussed topics relevant to the BioSCape Science Team as they endeavour to implement equitable science: Prior

Informed Consent (PIC), Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT) in relation to benefit sharing, and addressing the issues of intellectual property rights and the return of benefits to local communities.

- **Networking and socialising:** The day ended with ‘The BioSCape Social’ (a tradition in the making). Participants were exposed to the local culture and flavours firstly by a "Biodiversity-conscious wine-tasting" experience hosted by Rupert Koopman - giving a fynbos conservation perspective and also how the wine industry is contributing to conservation stewardship. This was followed by a “harvest table” dinner showcasing local South African cuisine.

Day 3: Field Trips - Walking in the surrounding landscapes and seascapes

Day 3 was dedicated to walking in the landscape as a way to experience the social-ecological significance of this region, to get a better sense of the local context and how science influences management of social ecological systems on the ground.

There were several field trip itinerary options that participants were able to choose from:

- Harold Porter Botanical Gardens (operated by SANBI) included a guided tour of the gardens and opportunity for a walk up the mountain or to the waterfalls, the Garden is renowned for its waterfalls and amber pools. It is situated in the centre of the coastal Fynbos where the mountain slopes include heathlands, deep gorges with relict forests, flats and marshes with restios, sedges and bulbs. Workshop participants also encountered a troop of baboons and quickly learnt to keep food out of site to work together with the community in mitigating human/wildlife conflict and ensuring that the Baboon Management Programme is a success in the Bettys’ Bay area.
- Stony Point Nature Reserve (operated by CapeNature) provided workshop participants with a viewing of the land-based penguin colony, which is the third-largest breeding colony of African Penguins (*Spheniscus demersus*) globally and has shown a measurable increase in breeding pairs due to conservation efforts. Participants enjoyed several talks where they heard about the Mooi Uitsig Community Trust and CapeNature’s journey with the community and associated socio-economic benefits, and work done by Southern African Foundation For The Conservation Of Coastal Birds (SANCCOB).
- Kleinmond coastal and lagoon ecosystems are biologically diverse and productive, and thus included in the core set of estuaries that needs to be protected to meet biodiversity targets in SA (Turpie et al., 2012). Workshop participants got to visit one of SA’s most important nursery areas for the marine fish that sustain our fisheries. Management of these ecosystems takes place in partnership with the local community and regulation stipulates that 50% of the terrestrial marginal area be protected from development and excessive use.
- Palmiet river in the Kogelberg Nature Reserve (operated by CapeNature) hike allowed workshop participants to experience 18 000 ha of relatively “pristine” Fynbos vegetation and a high level of biological diversity in a protected area adjacent to agriculture and commercial pine plantations on the Reserve’s borders. Kogelberg has three patches of relict indigenous forest that are similar to the Knysna forests and include yellowwood, stinkwood and boekenhout trees. Notably, Palmiet plants play an important ecological role in stabilizing the river bed and river banks from erosion. The biosphere concept that the reserve has adopted accommodates both conservation and development ecotourism needs.

Day 4: Understanding, communicating and planning for biodiversity research in the SA-context

Day 4 built on Day 2's knowledge exchange that aimed to enhance biodiversity conservation and the sustainability of landscapes and seascapes in the GCFR. The day began with a panel discussion on understanding local data user and decision-maker needs related to monitoring freshwater quality and quantity, managing freshwater and coastal aquatics and wetlands, and disaster risk reduction. It was followed by five BioSCAPE research talks sharing with the multi-stakeholder audience on why their research is important for applications that can advance biodiversity research and support decision-making. Based on the accumulated knowledge over the past four days of the Applications Workshop, participants engaged in a self-reflective exercise to compile a 'wishlist' for remote sensing in biodiversity (see Appendix 3). They were encouraged to review, expand upon and explore potential synergies and opportunities from collective efforts. The next session included an overview of the planned BioSCAPE short documentary film (release date: end-2024) which will capture the scientific data journey of BioSCAPE but also an important biodiversity and collaboration story of hope that needs to be shared with the world. The day concluded with an 'Open' session for logistical field work and flight planning during the campaign (16 October-27 November 2023). Although this was mostly for the Science Team, the intention of this session was to allow for researchers, collaborators, and various governmental and non-governmental SA stakeholders to participate in the campaign planning collaboratively and transparently. Click [here for Day 4 slides](#) by:

Panelists

- Nancy Job (South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) - Lead for Freshwater Biodiversity Programme) - Slides 11-12
- Melissa Lintnaar-Strauss (Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS) - Control Environmental Officer) - Slides 13-15
- Tommy Bornman (South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) - Elwandle Coastal Node Manager) - Slides 16-17
- Lwandile Nokoyo (Western Cape Dept of Local Government - Deputy Director: Risk Reduction Planning) - Slides 18-19

Research Talks

- Madeline Slimp (Stavros et al. - Biodiversity Across Scales: Mapping Taxonomic, Phylogenetic, and Functional Diversity with eDNA, Field Surveys, and Remote Sensing Data) - Slides 22-26
- Jan van Aardt (van Aardt et al. - RadSCAPE: Radiative Transfer Simulation and Validation of the Dynamic Structural and Spectral Properties of the Vegetation of the Cape) - Slides 27-31
- Kerry Cawse-Nicholson (Cawse-Nicholson et al. - Intrinsic Dimensionality and Data Fusion to Monitor Cape Biodiversity) - Slides 32-34
- Adriaan van Niekerk (van Niekerk et al. - Development of New Hyperspectral Capabilities across Aquatic, Atmospheric and Terrestrial Domains (HyperCAAT)) - Slides 35-38
- Phil Brodrick (Brodrick - BioSCAPE Multi-Sensor Data Integration) - Slides 39-49
- Jeremy Shelton (Fishwater Films) - Slides 58-71

Summarised insights

- **Panel discussion:** Overall, the panelists highlight the importance of remote sensing and GIS in various fields such as biodiversity, water resource management, coastal research, and disaster management. They also identify challenges and constraints that need to be addressed for better utilization of these tools. For example, the Department of Local Government that focuses on disaster risk reduction planning recognizes GIS and remote sensing as key tools for hazard and vulnerability mapping, damage assessment, and evacuation exercises. Constraints include data availability and technical capacity at local municipalities. Moreover, SANBI's Freshwater Biodiversity Programme is responsible for developing evidence and synthesizing knowledge to inform national and provincial departments.

They face constraints such as small teams, limited remote sensing and data science expertise, and a limited budget. They aim to operationalize remote sensing more systematically and establish a technical working group. The Department of Water and Sanitation already uses GIS tools for providing comments on land use applications, monitoring water resources, and producing reports on dam levels and water supply systems. Thus, further incorporation of remote sensing and GIS will aid in improved water resource management in the region. SAEON has procured their own airborne remote sensing platform and emphasize the need for more variables and expertise in satellite remote sensing as there is a lack of available data close to the shore and high cloud cover.

- **BioSCAPE lightning science talks:** Representatives from the BioSCAPE Science Team presented on various applications opportunities related to research topics including the following:
 - *PI - Rossi:* Mapping biodiversity with eDNA, field surveys, and remote sensing data across multiple scales. This work will explore the relationship between phylogenetic, taxonomic, and functional diversity along the Berg and Eerste River systems and show the importance of understanding water movement in predicting biodiversity patterns. It also highlights the importance of collaboration with river management partners and landowners to engage them and serve their interests and needs as well as the challenges associated with sampling and getting access permissions within a multi-functional SES.
 - *PI - van Aardt:* RadSCAPE is assessing the effects of fire on plant biodiversity by studying leaf traits over different temporal and spatial scales by using a physics-based simulation tool, validated with real data, to assess trait assessment as a function of post-fire recovery stage. By developing algorithms for tracking post-fire recovery and biodiversity, this work will track how environmental change affects ecosystem processes. It will also help land managers understand when it becomes difficult or impossible to monitor the health of an ecosystem (i.e. 'ecological condition' for ecosystem threat assessments).
 - *PI - Cawse-Nicholson:* Exploring the relationship between spectral diversity and evapotranspiration of plant biodiversity by providing broad scale information on areas that are "unusual" that might have conservation pressure in the GCFR. This work will help to better understand ecological infrastructure by mapping areas of exceptionally unique, high alpha diversity for conservation prioritisation.
 - *PI - van Niekerk:* HyperCAAT is developing a proof of concept for new hyperspectral capabilities by pooling expertise across thematic domains (aquatic, atmospheric and terrestrial) and constructing large synthetic data sets, which will improve our atmospheric correction methods for hyperspectral data in different conditions. This high-level approach is unique compared to the other BioSCAPE projects as it is being executed by an all-South African team and aims to train artificial intelligence models by using in situ data to enhance our understanding of remote sensing to benefit future BioSCAPE-like campaigns. For example, collecting data through radiometric buoy deployment in Walker Bay and Theewaterskloof/Steenbras dam and comparing multispectral and hyperspectral data will enhance our understanding of remote sensing and the trade-off between spectral resolution and signal sensitivity.
 - *PI - Brodrick:* Lastly, BioSCAPE has invested in a multi-sensor data integration as a cross-project data processing approach during the 6-week data collection period of the campaign by including an open-access data portal which includes flightlines and quick looks of the airborne data collected. This approach is optimised for low bandwidth, preliminary mosaics, and field planning support.

- **Science Communication:** We recognise that science communication is an important part of making BioSCAPE science applicable as we aim to raise awareness, appreciation and support for biodiversity and the people and projects working to protect it (#BioSCAPE #SpecialTimeAndSpecialPlace). We spent some time exploring the potential of filming BioSCAPE's short documentary film (Jeremy Shelton; Fishwater Films). A proposed draft film plan was presented to workshop participants, providing an overview of how the film could spotlight the research, institutions and researcher-end-user collaborations. Participants provided written feedback on their perceptions of what the most visually exciting part of their work is and reflections on what outcomes of the BioSCAPE research would benefit their work. Additionally, several interviews with project PIs, Early Career Researchers (ECRs), NASA remote sensing specialists and programme managers, and end-users were conducted to showcase how this ground-breaking project is giving new hope for measuring and managing biodiversity in this corner of Africa, and potentially globally.

Day 5: Reflecting on BioSCAPE science applications opportunities

Day 5 began with Adam Wilson providing an overview of BioSCAPE's planned Outreach / Education activities. Thereafter, Erin Hestir gave workshop participants a flight planning and campaign logistics overview which was followed by another 'Open' session to follow up with collaborators and networks (e.g. BioSCAPE ERCs huddle). We closed the workshop with a session that allowed for self- and group-reflection on BioSCAPE science applications opportunities. The Think-Pair-Share method was used and the following was shared during plenary feedback. Click [here](#) for Day 5 slides.

Outreach

- **7-8 October 2023** - NASA Space Apps Challenge was hosted virtually and in-person at four South African sites: [Pretoria](#), [Stellenbosch](#), [Franschhoek](#) and [Cape Town](#). The BioSCAPE-related challenge is titled, "[Explore a Biodiversity Hotspot with Imaging Spectroscopy](#)".
- **23-26 October 2023** - SAEON Graduate Student Network Conference/"The Indibano" was hosted at the South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO), Cape Town
- **21, 22, 23, 29 and 30 November, and 1 December 2023** - GLOBE Outreach Schools Programme in collaboration with SAEON, SAATA, and Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve will be hosted at the aquarium in Seapoint (managed by the Department of Forestry and Fisheries (DFFE) in South Africa).

Summarised insights

- The design of the workshop recognized the significance of involving end-users from the beginning, promoting the use and integration of BioSCAPE products, and ensuring sustainability in terms of resources, technology, and decisions.
- The workshop emphasized the importance of tracking existing impactful products, brainstorming new proposals, and learning from both failures and successes within the BioSCAPE collaborative research project to enhance communication and understanding of BioSCAPE products. Integrating values, decision-making, and equitable practices is crucial in biodiversity conservation and research.
- The workshop created awareness of the invasive species problem, thoroughly addressing the challenges and opportunities related to invasive species. However, BioSCAPE may potentially overlook the detailed needs in this area given the short timeframe of the research.
- Participants highlighted the need for knowledge exchange, learning and capacity-building and to bridge the 'language' gap between scientists and practitioners, suggesting the development of a

glossary of terms to improve communication. It was also noted that the workshop did not adequately explore the potential applications of open data in urban and agricultural contexts, limiting the discussion to biodiversity science.

Appendix 2: Template for Value Creation Framework breakout session

Appendix 3: Remote sensing for biodiversity 'wishlist'

Ecosystem Function / Character / Land Use	Land-cover change Ecosystem Refugia Settlement expansion Threatened habitats Rehabilitation success / failure Degradation rates
Distributions	Vegetation plot data (extensive) - <i>Species distributions & fragmentation</i> - <i>Remnant vegetation</i> - <i>Alien vegetation</i> Wetlands / Lakes (including dynamics)

	- Berg, Breede, Oliphants Rivers
Attributes / Qualities	<p>Functional Traits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemistry, metabolics, chlorophyll, LAI, Carotenoids, etc. <p>Spectra</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leaves / plants - Soil, Rocks, background (by post-fire age) <p>Vegetation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Canopy height / structure <p>Geochemistry (nitrogen/phosphorus)</p> <p>Soil Moisture / Evapotranspiration</p> <p>Carbon / Biomass (t/ha)</p>
Remote Sensing Products / Technology	<p>High-quality, very high spatial resolution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shortwave infrared - Temporal frequency (multiple times per day) <p>Timeseries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dynamic ecosystem state maps? <p>High accuracy topographic</p> <p>Lidar</p>
Capacity building / Training / Access	<p>Data Formats and Access (user-friendly)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cloud computing - Google Earth Engine, Microsoft Planetary Computer - Open Access to Publications <p>Data sharing & Collaboration</p> <p>Local scientists & End Users</p> <p>Support/Funding</p>

Participants engaged in a self-reflective exercise to identify end-user needs and desired data products for remote sensing in biodiversity. Their input was compiled into a comprehensive wishlist to guide future discussions and collaborations. Participants were encouraged to review and expand upon their responses, consider any overlooked elements, and explore potential synergies and opportunities from collective efforts.

Appendix 4: List of (a) SA institutions, (b) UK and (c) US Institutions represented at the workshop

 (a) South Africa (SA)			
Representation	Institution name and logo	Description	Website link
End-user: Government	<p>Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) - National Government</p> <p>forestry, fisheries & the environment <small>Department: Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA</small></p>	<p>The legal mandate and core business of the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) are to manage, protect and conserve South Africa's environment and natural resources. The mandate is informed by section 24 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (Act No. 108 of 1996), which affords everyone the right to (a) an environment that is not harmful to their health or well-being; and (b) to have the environment protected for the benefit of</p>	<p>https://www.dffe.gov.za/</p>

		present and future generations, through reasonable legislative and other measures	
	<p>Dept. of Envir. Affairs and Dev Planning (DEA&DP) - Western Cape Provincial Government</p>	The DEA&DP must ensure the resilient, sustainable, and robust future of the Western Cape. The department has various subsets, including hands-on conservation efforts, urban planning and upgrading, and water and resource management.	https://www.westerncape.gov.za/ea/dp/
	<p>Department of Science and Innovation (DSI) - National Government</p>	The DSI uses research and innovation to boost socio-economical development in South Africa. With the National R&D Strategy at its core, the department seeks to reap all opportunities, innovations, and benefits from science, engineering, and technology.	https://www.dst.gov.za/
	<p>Dept of Water and Sanitation (DWS) - National Government</p>	The motto of DWS: "Water is life, sanitation is dignity." The department serves as the custodian of South Africa's water resources. It has ambitious goals to equip all citizens with easy access to clean water, and with programs like Blue Deal SA well underway, the department has already set the foundation to do just that.	https://www.dws.gov.za/default.aspx
	<p>Disaster Risk Reduction (DDR) - Department of Local Government</p>	The Disaster Risk Reduction Directorate is responsible for establishing and maintaining institutional disaster management capacity and implement effective risk reduction activities. Its function is to facilitate and coordinate the reduction of potential risks posed by hazards.	https://www.westerncape.gov.za/your_gov/431/
Boundary agency: Government parastatal	<p>CapeNature</p>	CapeNature is the chief custodian of the Western Cape's natural environment. It puts conservation into practice by nourishing 113 nature reserves and supplying local farmers, communities, and private landowners with eco-friendly tools for sustainable agriculture. Its eco-tourism highlights the unmatched biodiversity of the Western Cape while providing every reason to put nature first in SA's future.	https://www.cape-nature.co.za/
	<p>Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR)</p>	The Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) is a science and technology research organization to improve the quality of life and socio-economic development in South Africa. It does this through partnerships in the public and private sectors, research, and the creation and distribution of new technology. CSIR's core values are excellence, people, integrity, and collaboration.	https://www.csir.co.za/
	<p>South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON)</p>	SAEON is a research facility within the NRF that focuses on environmental change. The NRF oversees and advances the research infrastructure of South Africa to transcend scientific endeavors to new heights. All NRF efforts derive from equity, sustainability, and transformation, and it is the agency's highest goal to dissolve legacies of apartheid that linger in the research workforce and beyond. SAEON analyzes and investigates the evolution of SA biomes. The data from these missions have been tailored for open access, seamlessly supporting policy and decision making. SAEON also prizes its youth engagement programs, which inspire up-and-coming citizens to pursue science careers.	https://www.saeon.ac.za/
	<p>South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)</p>	SANBI focuses on studying and protecting biodiversity and increasing access to data and information. Its work helps guide public policy on conservation and ecosystem management. By managing the National Botanical and Zoological Gardens and designing education programs, SANBI teaches the public about biodiversity and its importance in ecosystem function.	https://www.sanbi.org/
	<p>South African National Parks (SANParks)</p>	SANParks works to conserve South Africa's biodiversity and encourage sustainable tourism by working with local communities for socio-economic development and education. It operates nearly 20 national parks that are ecologically and culturally significant. SANParks focuses on community-based conservation and conscious tourism.	https://www.sanparks.org/

	 South African NATIONAL PARKS		
	South African National Space Agency (SANSA) SANSA SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SPACE AGENCY	SANSA has four program areas. The earth observation projects use satellite and other earth observation data to help guide policy and decision-making, sustainable development, socio-economic development, resource management, and disaster management. Space engineering projects focus on building and launching satellites, and space operations work in mission control and satellite tracking. SANSA's space science projects focus on studying near-space environments, magnetic fields, and weather patterns in South Africa and Antarctica.	https://www.sansa.org.za/
End-user: NGOs/NPCs	BirdLife BirdLife SOUTH AFRICA <i>Giving Conservation Wings</i>	BirdLife South Africa is part of BirdLife International. It works to protect birds and bird habitats as well as biodiversity as a whole through research and conservation projects. It promotes the sustainable and equitable use of natural resources and works to connect people to nature.	https://www.birdlife.org.za/who-we-are/about/
	Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve Cape Winelands BIOSPHERE RESERVE	Since 2007, the CWBR has been overseeing South Africa's 5th biosphere reserve as a non-profit company. Its model has three priorities: conservation, sustainability, and logistic support. CWBR projects have an extensive impact through their social-ecological framework.	https://www.capewinelandsbiosphere.co.za/
Academic institutions	Natural Science Collections Facility (NSCF) Natural Science Collections Facility SOUTH AFRICA	The NSCF is a virtual Facility, comprised of a network of institutions that hold natural science collections that are accessible to external researchers. The NSCF was established as part of the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI)'s Research Infrastructure Roadmap and co-ordinated by SANBI.	https://nscf.org.za/learn-more-about-us/
	Stellenbosch University Stellenbosch UNIVERSITY IYUNIVESITHI UNIVERSITEIT	In Stellenbosch, South Africa, SU has some of the best world-class agriculture and forestry programs. Our researchers from Stellenbosch will use remote sensing data to map plant diversity.	http://www.sun.ac.za/english
	University of Cape Town (UCT) UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN IYUNIVESITHI YASEKAPA - UNIVERSITEIT VAN KAAPSTAD	Once a boys' high school, UCT has evolved into Africa's top-rated university. UCT houses a diverse student and staff body and has established grounds for equity and inclusion. It encourages high community engagement among its students and has set the bar for how Africa-based creations and innovations can transform the world.	https://www.uct.ac.za/
	University of Kwazulu Natal (UKZN) UNIVERSITY OF KWAZULU-NATAL INYUVESI YAKWAZULU-NATALI	Set in Durban, South Africa, the University of Kwazulu Natal ranks as one of the best universities in South Africa. Our partners there are part of the team studying the biochemical and biophysical properties of aquatic environments.	https://ukzn.ac.za/
	University of Pretoria (UP) UNIVERSITEIT VAN PRETORIA UNIVERSITY OF PRETORIA YUNIBESITHI YA PRETORIA	At UP, students immerse in a research-intensive university and an environment that elicits social change through activism. It has seven campuses (the largest is in the heart of Hatfield, South Africa). Through Sci-Enza, UP produces interactive STEM sessions for primary and secondary schools. The university also has a food garden that feeds and trains the local community.	https://www.up.ac.za/
	University of Venda (UniVen) University of Venda	The University of Venda is located in Thohoyandou, South Africa, and is known for its research in the earth sciences. UV partners will be studying cyanobacteria and aquatic vegetation in freshwater ecosystems.	https://www.univen.ac.za/

	<p>University of the Western Cape (UWC)</p> <p>UNIVERSITY of the WESTERN CAPE</p>	<p>The University of the Western Cape is based in Cape Town, South Africa. It has consistently ranked as one of the best universities in South Africa. Our partners at UWC are involved in multiple projects from terrestrial and aquatic environments.</p>	<p>https://www.uwc.ac.za/</p>
	<p>University of the Witwatersrand (WITS), Johannesburg</p>	<p>Wits values open minds and full hearts on its campus, inspiring activism and progress from the economic and industrial heartland of Africa, Johannesburg. The university has a history of protesting inequality, most prominently during apartheid legislation, and continues to welcome all students as one. Wits also remain active in the rural scene through Wits Rural Campus to fight against socio-economic disparities in regions with limited health research and access.</p>	<p>https://www.wits.ac.za/</p>

<p>(b) United Kingdom (UK)</p>			
Representation	Institution name and logo	Description	Website link
<p>End-user/ boundary agency</p>	<p>United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC)</p>	<p>The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) is the leading global authority on the environment. UNEP's mission is to inspire, inform, and enable nations and peoples to improve their quality of life without compromising that of future generations. The UNEP World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC) is a global centre of excellence on biodiversity and nature's contribution to society and the economy. We work at the interface of science, policy, and practice to tackle the global crisis facing nature and support the transition to a sustainable future for people and the planet.</p>	<p>https://www.unep.org/who-we-are/about-us</p>

<p>(c) United States (US)</p>			
Representation	Institution name and logo	Description	Website link
<p>BioScape funder: Governmental agency</p>	<p>National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Applied Sciences</p>	<p>As the designated civil space program for the US, NASA investigates space while studying the Earth and its climate. The agency has 20 centres that foster a global community of contractors, academic professionals, and commercial partners. NASA regularly cooperates with other space agencies to increase access to space discovery for all. NASA's Applied Sciences program uses earth observation data from satellites and other remote sensing instruments to guide decision-making. It partners with governments, institutions, non-profits, and individuals in assessing its work.</p>	<p>https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/about/our-work</p>
<p>NASA</p>	<p>NASA Ames Research Center</p>	<p>The vision of NASA Ames Research Center is to continue as a world-class research, technology, and development organization. It aims to advance humanity's understanding of Earth, space, and the universe through innovative and collaborative exploration and research missions, thus influencing the scientific and technological landscape for the betterment of society.</p>	<p>https://www.nasa.gov/ames/about-ames/</p>

	<p>NASA Goddard</p>	<p>Research at NASA's Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) emphasizes a broad study of global change, an interdisciplinary initiative addressing natural and man-made changes in our environment that occur on various time scales — from one-time forcings such as volcanic explosions, to seasonal and annual effects such as El Niño, and on up to the millennia of ice ages — and that affect the habitability of our planet.</p>	<p>https://www.nasa.gov/goddard-institute-for-space-studies/about/</p>
<p>End-user: NGOs/NPCs</p>	<p>Point Blue Conservation Science</p>	<p>Based in Petaluma, California, the then-bird observatory has evolved into an official Observer Organization in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Point Blue recognizes disproportionate environmental degradation in Black, Indigenous, Latinx, and other communities of color with lower socio-economic standing. The non-profit spearheads a daring mission to fuse sustainable and climate-smart practices into our daily lives, and it does so by putting historically excluded groups at the front of the conservation.</p>	<p>https://www.pointblue.org/</p>
<p>Academic Institutions</p>	<p>Jet Propulsion Lab, California Institute of Technology</p> <p>Jet Propulsion Laboratory California Institute of Technology</p>	<p>Caltech is the science and engineering powerhouse in Pasadena, California. It manages the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) for NASA and owns and operates other large-scale research facilities such as the Seismological Laboratory and a global network of astronomical observatories. JPL started as a group of Caltech graduate students and amateur rocket enthusiasts. It has since expanded and redirected to space exploration under the wings of NASA and the management of Caltech. JPL has had missions on every planet in the solar system and even explored deep space. Its goal is to continue exploring the universe and our planet Earth to advance understanding and embrace curiosity.</p>	<p>https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/</p>
	<p>Columbia University in the City of New York</p>	<p>Founded in 1754 by royal charter, Columbia has a distinguished history of discovery. The university continues to be a leader in the global research scene, reaping the benefits of NYC while sowing back into the community. Columbia has recently undertaken the President's Commission on the History of Race and Racism at Columbia. In doing so, it hopes to be transparent about its past while creating a more welcoming space for all.</p>	<p>https://www.columbia.edu/</p>
	<p>Rochester Institute of Technology</p>	<p>Home to Rochester, New York, RIT is a leading university that studies the intersections between science, technology, and media. Our partners at RIT will use remote sensing data to look at the canopy cover of native plant species in the Greater Cape Floristic Region and how native plants connect to post-fire recovery.</p>	<p>https://www.rit.edu/</p>
	<p>Sonoma State SONOMA STATE UNIVERSITY</p>	<p>SSU is home to Rohnert Park, California. It is known for its strong liberal arts and science programs. Our partner at Sonoma State will study the relationship between acoustic diversity and spectral diversity.</p>	<p>https://www.sonoma.edu/about</p>
	<p>Texas A&M University</p>	<p>From its opening in 1876 to now, TAMU has broken the glass ceilings in research, education, and athletics. It is proud to be a Hispanic Serving Institute and continues to make waves in diversity and inclusion while servicing the greater community. Each day at TAMU prepares another Aggie to manifest local and global impact.</p>	<p>https://www.tamu.edu/index.html</p>
	<p>University at Buffalo</p>	<p>The New York flagship university has fostered a supportive and ever-evolving higher education system for over 175 years. UB is well-known for its climate change consciousness and initiatives to protect our planet. It also values community-building and welcomes every student in as a family.</p>	<p>https://www.buffalo.edu/</p>
	<p>University of California, Los Angeles</p>	<p>As one of the top public universities in the US, UCLA holds a high standard in research, athletics, and service. It has launched the Data for Democracy project to celebrate its centennial. The initiative seeks to analyze critical information relating to jobs, housing, and park access in LA. The university also prioritizes publicly and globally accessible research through OpenUCLA.</p>	<p>https://www.ucla.edu/</p>

<p>University of California, Merced</p>	<p>From Merced, California, UC Merced has made numerous strides in sustainability efforts and environmental science research. One of the marine science team leads for BioSCape, Erin Hestir, is an associate professor here. The BioSCape aquatic projects will investigate aquatic vegetation diversity, algal blooms, and phytoplankton. They will also observe how these factors connect to water and food security.</p>	<p>https://www.ucmerced.edu/</p>
<p>University of California, Santa Cruz</p>	<p>UC Santa Cruz is located in Santa Cruz, California. It is known for its programs in environmental science and marine biology. Partners at UC Santa Cruz will use remote sensing and environmental DNA data to study functional, taxonomic, and phylogenetic diversity in the Greater Cape Floristic Region.</p>	<p>https://www.ucsc.edu/</p>
<p>University of Colorado, Boulder</p>	<p>The University of Colorado, Boulder's mission is shape tomorrow's leaders, be the top University for innovation, and to positively impact humanity. Their vision is to be a leader in addressing the humanitarian, social, and technological challenges of the twenty-first century.</p>	<p>https://www.colorado.edu/academicaffairs/about-academic-affairs</p>
<p>University of Connecticut</p>	<p>Based in Mansfield, Connecticut, UCONN is one of the top 50 public universities in the United States. The team at UCONN will compare spectral data to field data to assess the accuracy of remote sensing data that can be used to map plant vegetation.</p>	<p>https://uconn.edu/</p>
<p>University of Maryland, College Park</p>	<p>UMD is a service-driven university that sees student action today as tomorrow's solutions and opportunities. Since 2016, students have had the chance to answer to current social issues through the creation of the Do Good Institute, an initiative for a creative, hands-on community service experience. UMD also has bold goals in sustainability, with hopes to be carbon neutral by 2025.</p>	<p>https://www.umd.edu/</p>
<p>University of Minnesota</p>	<p>The University of Minnesota is located in Minneapolis, Minnesota. UM is one of the top 25 public universities in the US. Our partners at the university are part of the team studying plant evolutionary ecology.</p>	<p>https://twin-cities.umn.edu/</p>
<p>University of Wisconsin-Madison</p>	<p>UW has prioritized intentionality in its partnership with the local and global community. It recently underwent the Public History Project to remember and educate the university's past struggles with inequality and integration. Above all, UW has an undeterred spirit of public service, what it coins the Wisconsin Idea, and has sought to serve the greater community since its founding in 1848.</p>	<p>https://www.wisc.edu/</p>
<p>Utah State University</p>	<p>Located in the small but robust town of Logan, Utah, USU is a public university with excellence in research and athletics. It has always had a relationship with nature. USU's Janet Quinney Lawson Institute for Land, Water & Air equips students and faculty with the necessary tools to observe and conserve the Earth.</p>	<p>https://www.usu.edu/</p>

Appendix 5: List of Application Workshop participants

Institution	Representation per institution	Type of representation	Country participation
BirdLife South Africa	2	End-user	SA
Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve	2	End-user	SA
CapeNature	2	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
Columbia University	2	Academic	US

Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR)	6	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
Fishwater Films	1	Private	SA
NASA Ames Research Center	3	NASA	US
NASA Goddard	3	NASA	US
NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory	3	NASA	US
Natural Science Collections Facility (NSCF)	1	Academic	SA
Point Blue Conservation Science	1	End-user	US
Private	1	Private	SA
Rochester Institute of Technology	1	Academic	US
Sonoma State University	1	Academic	US
South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE)	1	End-user	SA
South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON)	3	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)	7	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
South African National Department of Water and Sanitation	1	End-user	SA
South African National Parks (SANParks)	4	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
South African National Space Agency (SANSA)	3	Boundary Agency/ End-user	SA
Stellenbosch University	3	Academic	SA
Texas A&M University	1	Academic	US
UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC)	1	Boundary Agency/ End-user	UK
University at Buffalo	3	Academic	US
University at Buffalo (UB) + University of Cape Town (UCT)	2	Academic	SA
University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)	1	Academic	US
University of California, Merced	2	Academic	US
University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC)	2	Academic	US
University of Cape Town (UCT)	3	Academic	SA
University of Colorado, Boulder	1	Academic	US
University of Connecticut	2	Academic	US
University of Kwa-Zulu Natal (UKZN)	1	Academic	SA
University of Maryland	2	Academic	US
University of Minnesota	1	Academic	SA
University of Pretoria (UP)	3	Academic	SA
University of the Western Cape (UWC)	4	Academic	SA
University of Venda	2	Academic	SA
University of Wisconsin, Madison	2	Academic	US
University of Witwatersrand	1	Academic	SA
Western Cape Government (DEA&DP)	5	End-user	SA
Western Cape Government (Dept of Agri)	1	End-user	SA

Western Cape Government (Local Dept: DRR)	2	End-user	SA
Western Cape Government: Department of Water and Sanitation	1	End-user	SA

Notes: ‘Boundary agencies’ are institutions that have a decision-making role, but are also mandated to collect data and perform research in support of decision-making needs, for example, the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), South African National Parks (SANParks), the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI).

Appendix 6: Leads for future engagement with additional institutions as suggested by workshop participants.

Academic institutions	Some funded BioSCape PIs
	University of Wisconsin-Eau Claire in the US
	University of the Witwatersrand’s computer science and machine learning specialists
End-user: SA Government	Western Cape Government Department of Agriculture
	Urban and spatial planning
Boundary agencies: SA Government parastatal agencies	SANParks: Biodiversity Social Projects Unit and Park Planning Division (park expansion etc) of SANParks.
	Agricultural Research Council (ARC)
End-user: NGOs and NPCs	World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)
	The Nature Conservancy (TNC)
	Biodiversity and Development Institute (BDI)
	Conservation South Africa (CSA)
Civil society	Representatives from local communities

Appendix 7: SA institutions that participated in ARSET Training

Institution name	No. of participants	Institution represented at Applications Workshop (Y/N)	Type of representation
Agricultural Research Council, South Africa	1	N	Boundary Agency/End-user
Astrofica Technologies	2	N	Boundary Agency
Cape Winelands Biosphere Reserve	2	Y	End-user
CapeNature	10	Y	Boundary Agency/End-user
Conservation Outcomes	1	N	Boundary Agency/End-user
ConservAxiom Trust	1	N	End-user
Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR)	2	Y	Boundary Agency/End-user
Dyer Island Conservation Trust	1	N	End-user
Endangered Wildlife Trust	2	N	End-user
Exigent	1	N	Boundary Agency
Ezemvelo KwaZulu-Natal Wildlife	2	N	End-user
Freshwater Research Centre	1	N	Boundary Agency/End-user
Gauteng City, Region Observatory	1	N	End-user
GeaSphere	1	N	Boundary Agency
GeoNest Pty Ltd	1	N	Boundary Agency
GOZO Consulting	1	N	Boundary Agency
GroundTruth	1	N	Boundary Agency
Mpumalanga Tourism & Parks Agency (MPTA)	2	N	Boundary Agency/End-user
Nature Connect	1	N	Boundary Agency
NOEZ Consulting & Design	1	N	Boundary Agency
Noordhoek Environmental Action Group	1	N	End-user
Quemic Africa	1	N	End-user
Sol Plaatje University	1	N	Academic
South African Environmental Observation Network	7	Y	Boundary Agency/End-user
South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)	3	Y	Boundary Agency/End-user
South African National Parks (SANParks)	5	Y	Boundary Agency/End-user
Stellenbosch University	2	Y	Academic
Stellenbosch University Botanical Gardens	1	N	Academic
University of Cape Town	13	Y	Academic
University of Limpopo	4	N	Academic
University of Mpumalanga	1	N	Academic
University of Pretoria	11	Y	Academic
University of the Western Cape	9	Y	Academic
University of the Witwatersrand	2	Y	Academic
Western Cape Department of Agriculture	1	Y	End-user
Western Cape Government, Environmental Affairs & Development Planning	4	Y	End-user
Wildlife Conservation Solutions	1	N	End-user
Other/Unknown	3	N/A	N/A

ARSET workshop was held virtually in April, 2023. Rows highlighted show overlap in organizational representation at the Applications Workshop. ARSET workshop materials are available at <https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/get-involved/training/english/arset-biodiversity-applications-airborne-imag-q-systems>

Appendix 8: List of Acronyms

ARC	Agricultural Research Council
ARLs	Application Readiness Levels
ARSET	Applied Remote Sensing Training Program
AVIRIS-NG	Airborne Visible - Infrared Imaging Spectrometer - Next Generation
BioSCape	Biodiversity Survey of the Cape
CFRP	Cape Floristic Region Partnership
COP	Community of Practice
CSIR	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
DEA&DP	Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning
DFFE	Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
DWS	Department of Water and Sanitation
ECOSTRESS	ECOSystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station
ECRs	Early Career Researchers
EFTEON	Expanded Freshwater and Terrestrial Environmental Observation Network
EMIT	Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation
EO	Earth Observation
GCFR	Greater Cape Floristic Region
GIS	geographic information systems
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
HyTES	Hyperspectral Thermal Emission Spectrometer
IAPs	Invasive Alien Plants
LVIS	Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NBA	National Biodiversity Assessment
NEMBA	National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (No. 10 of 2004)
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRF	National Research Foundation
NWA	National Water Act (No 36 of 1998)
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
PRISM	Portable Remote Imaging Spectrometer
RLE	Red List of Ecosystems
RLI	Red List Index
SA	South Africa
SAEON	South African Environmental Observation Network
SANBI	South African National Biodiversity Institute
SANCCOB	Southern African Foundation For The Conservation Of Coastal Birds
SANParks	South African National Parks
SANSA	South African National Space Agency
SCP	Systematic Conservation Planning

SES	social-ecological systems
SMCE	Science Managed Cloud Environment
SWSAs	Strategic Water Source Areas
UBCEG	Upper Breede Collaborative Extension Group
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
US	United States